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Research Article

**ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION
FOR ESTIMATION OF LEVOTHYROXINE AND
LIOTHYRONINE IN API AND PHARMACEUTICAL
FORMULATION BY USING RP-HPLC.**

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Abstract:

A new, simple and accurate, precise RP-HPLC method was developed for simultaneous determination of Levothyroxine and Liothyronine in bulk and in combined pharmaceutical dosage form. The separation of Levothyroxine and Liothyronine was achieved within 8 minutes on an Agilent Zorbax (C18) (150mm x 4.6mm, 5µm) column using Methanol: Acetonitrile (25:75v/v) as the mobile phase. Detection was carried out using wavelength at 265nm. The method showed adequate sensitivity concerning linearity, accuracy and precision over the range 100-500µg/ml and 30-70µg/ml for Levothyroxine and Liothyronine, respectively. Careful validation proved advantages of high sensitivity, accuracy, precision, selectivity, robust and suitability for quality control laboratories. The developed method was robust as the %RSD was within the range and without effecting system suitability parameters. The proposed method is suitable for simultaneous determination of Levothyroxine and Liothyronine in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form.

Keywords: *Levothyroxine and Liothyronine, RP-HPLC, Validation, Precision, Robustness, ICH Guidelines.***Corresponding author:****Koppu Udaya Bhanu Sri,**Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis,
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INTRODUCTION:

Chromatography is a laboratory technique for the separation of a mixture. The mixture is dissolved in a fluid called the mobile phase, which carries it through a structure holding another material called the stationary phase. The various constituents of the mixture travel at different speeds, causing them to separate. The separation is based on differential partitioning between the mobile and stationary phases. Subtle differences in a compound's **partition coefficient** result in differential retention on the stationary phase and thus affect the separation.

Chromatography may be preparative or analytical. The purpose of preparative chromatography is to separate the components of a mixture for later use, and is thus a form of **purification**. Analytical chromatography is done normally with smaller amounts of material and is for establishing the presence or measuring the relative proportions of analytes in a mixture. The two are not mutually exclusive.

Chromatography is based on the principle where molecules in mixture applied onto the surface or into the solid, and fluid stationary phase (stable phase) is separating from each other while moving with the aid of a mobile phase. The factors effective on this separation process include molecular characteristics related to adsorption (liquid-solid), partition (liquid-solid), and affinity or differences among their molecular weights [1, 2]. Because of these differences, some components of the mixture stay longer in the stationary phase, and they move slowly in the chromatography system, while others pass rapidly into mobile phase, and leave the system faster [3].

Based on this approach three components form the basis of the chromatography technique.

- Stationary phase: This phase is always composed of a “solid” phase or “a layer of a liquid adsorbed on the surface a solid support”.
- Mobile phase: This phase is always composed of “liquid” or a “gaseous component.”
- Separated molecules

The type of interaction between stationary phase, mobile phase, and substances contained in the mixture is the basic component effective on separation of molecules from each other. Chromatography methods based on partition are very effective on separation, and identification of small molecules as amino acids, carbohydrates, and fatty acids. However, affinity chromatographies (ie. ion-exchange chromatography) are more effective in the separation of macromolecules as nucleic acids, and proteins. Paper chromatography

is used in the separation of proteins, and in studies related to protein synthesis; gas-liquid chromatography is utilized in the separation of alcohol, ester, lipid, and amino groups, and observation of enzymatic interactions, while molecular-sieve chromatography is employed especially for the determination of molecular weights of proteins. Agarose-gel chromatography is used for the purification of RNA, DNA particles, and viruses [4].

Stationary phase in chromatography, is a solid phase or a liquid phase coated on the surface of a solid phase. Mobile phase flowing over the stationary phase is a gaseous or liquid phase. If mobile phase is liquid, it is termed as liquid chromatography (LC), and if it is gas then it is called gas chromatography (GC). Gas chromatography is applied for gases, and mixtures of volatile liquids, and solid material. Liquid chromatography is used especially for thermal unstable, and non-volatile samples [5].

The purpose of applying chromatography which is used as a method of quantitative analysis apart from its separation, is to achieve a satisfactory separation within a suitable time interval. Various chromatography methods have been developed to that end. Some of them include column chromatography, thin-layer chromatography (TLC), paper chromatography, gas chromatography, ion exchange chromatography, gel permeation chromatography, high-pressure liquid chromatography, and affinity chromatography [6].

- Column chromatography
- Ion-exchange chromatography
- Gel-permeation (molecular sieve) chromatography
- Affinity chromatography
- Paper chromatography
- Thin-layer chromatography
- Gas chromatography
- Dye-ligand chromatography
- Hydrophobic interaction chromatography
- Pseudo affinity chromatography
- High-pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC)

High-pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC)

Using this chromatography technique, it is possible to perform structural, and functional analysis, and purification of many molecules within a short time, This technique yields perfect results in the separation, and identification of amino acids, carbohydrates, lipids, nucleic acids, proteins, steroids, and other

biologically active molecules, In HPLC, mobile phase passes through columns under 10–400 atmospheric pressure, and with a high (0.1–5 cm//sec) flow rate. In this technique, use of small particles, and application of high pressure on the rate of solvent flow increases separation power, of HPLC and the analysis is completed within a short time.

Essential components of a HPLC device are solvent depot, high- pressure pump, commercially prepared column, detector, and recorder. Duration of separation is controlled.

Essential components of a HPLC device are solvent depot, high- pressure pump, commercially prepared column, detector, and recorder. Duration of separation is controlled with the aid of a computerized system, and material is accrued.

Types of HPLC

There are following variants of HPLC, depending upon the phase system (stationary) in the process:

1. Normal Phase HPLC

This method separates analytes on the basis of polarity. NP-HPLC uses polar stationary phase and non-polar mobile phase. Therefore, the stationary phase is usually silica and typical mobile phases are hexane, methylene chloride, chloroform, diethyl ether, and mixtures of these.

Polar samples are thus retained on the polar surface of the column packing longer than less polar materials.

2. Reverse Phase HPLC

The stationary phase is nonpolar (hydrophobic) in nature, while the mobile phase is a polar liquid, such as mixtures of water and methanol or acetonitrile. It works on the principle of hydrophobic interactions hence the more nonpolar the material is, the longer it will be retained.

3. Size-exclusion HPLC

The column is filled with material having precisely controlled pore sizes, and the particles are separated according to its their molecular size. Larger molecules are rapidly washed through the column; smaller molecules penetrate inside the porous of the packing particles and elute later.

4. Ion-Exchange HPLC

The stationary phase has an ionically charged surface of opposite charge to the sample ions. This technique is used almost exclusively with ionic or ionizable samples.

The stronger the charge on the sample, the stronger it will be attracted to the ionic surface and thus, the longer it will take to elute. The mobile phase is an aqueous buffer, where both pH and ionic strength are used to control elution time.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Instruments used:

HPLC from WATERS, software: Empower 2, Alliance 2695 separation module. 996 PDA detector.

Chemicals used:

Levothyroxine and Liothyronine from Sura Pharma Labs, Water and Methanol for HPLC from LICHROSOLV (MERCK) and Acetonitrile for HPLC from Merck

Method validation

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 250 ml (25%) of Methanol and 750 ml of Acetonitrile (75%) a were mixed and degassed in digital ultra sonicator for 15 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Optimized Chromatogram:

Instrument used :	Waters HPLC with auto sampler and PDA Detector 996 model.
Temperature :	37°C
Column :	Agilent Zorbax (C18) (150mm x 4.6mm, 5 μ m) column
Mobile phase :	Methanol: Acetonitrile (25:75v/v)
Flow rate :	1ml/min
Wavelength :	265nm
Injection volume :	10 μ l
Run time :	8 min

Fig 7.6: Optimized Chromatogram

Table 7.6: Observation of Optimized Chromatogram

S.No.	Peak Name	Retention Time	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP Resolution
1	Levothyroxine	1.692	1658785	385669	1.69	7586	10.85
2	Liothyronine	3.246	425631	65245	1.58	6235	

Inference:

1. The Retention Time is decreased observed from chromatogram by increasing flow rate.
2. The retention time was Levothyroxine and Liothyronine was found to be 1.692 and 3.246 respectively.
3. The tailing is not more than two and plate count observed is more than 2500. Pass all the system suitability parameters.
4. The peak shapes are good with good resolution and less Retention Time and more theoretical levels, pass the system suitability parameters.

Standard Chromatogram

Table : Observation of Standard Chromatogram-1

S.No	Peak Name	Retention Time (min)	Area	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP Resolution
1	Levothyroxine	1.694	1659824	1.68	7595	10.89
2	Liothyronine	3.244	426521	1.59	6274	

Table: Observation of standard Chromatogram-2

S.No	Peak Name	Retention Time (min)	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Resolution
1	Levothyroxine	1.689	1658598	7599	1.68	10.86
2	Liothyronine	3.238	426598	6254	1.57	

Table: Observation of standard Chromatogram-3

S.No	Peak Name	Retention Time (min)	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Levothyroxine	1.692	1658985	7659	1.70
2	Liothyronine	3.246	425865	6359	1.59

Table: Observation of standard Chromatogram-4

S.No	Peak Name	Retention Time (min)	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Levothyroxine	1.688	1658579	7672	1.71
2	Liothyronine	3.265	435698	6295	1.60

Table 7.12: Observation of standard Chromatogram-5

S.No	Peak Name	Retention Time (min)	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Levothyroxine	1.688	1659852	7695	1.69
2	Liothyronine	3.265	436598	6498	1.59

Assay (Sample):**Table 7.13: Observation of sample Chromatogram -1**

S.No	Peak Name	Retention Time (min)	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Levothyroxine	1.691	1669558	7695	1.70
2	Liothyronine	3.242	436589	6359	1.61

Table 7.14: Observation of sample Chromatogram -2

S.No	Peak Name	Retention Time (min)	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Levothyroxine	1.694	1678598	7698	1.72
2	Liothyronine	3.240	436985	6557	1.59

Table 7.15: Observation of sample Chromatogram -3

S.No	Peak Name	Retention Time (min)	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Levothyroxine	1.694	1668985	7659	1.72
2	Liothyronine	3.234	436598	6347	1.61

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

System Suitability Results:

- 1) Tailing factor obtained from the standard injection is 1.69.
- 2) Theoretical plates obtained from the standard injection are 7586.

Assay limits for Levothyroxine and Liothyronine is 98-102%.

Accuracy:**Levothyroxine:****Table : Accuracy Observation of Levothyroxine**

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Average Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	879537	150	150.048	100.032	100.112%
100%	1743252	300	300.521	100.172	
150%	2609693	450	450.598	100.132	

Liothyronine:**Table: Accuracy Observation of Liothyronine**

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Average Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	224271	25	25.114	100.456%	100.16%
100%	445748.3	50	49.952	99.904%	
150%	670006.3	75	75.101	100.134%	

Precision:**Table 7.28: Observation of System Precision**

S. No	Sample Area 1	Sample Area 2
1	1658254	426598
2	1658952	426589
3	1654857	426985
4	1659854	426587
5	1653298	426515
Mean	1657043	426654.8
Std.dev	2820.29	187.5692
%RSD	0.1702	0.043963

Acceptance Criteria:

In the precision study %RSD was found to be less than 2%. For Levothyroxine **0.17%** and Liothyronine 0.04% which indicates that the system has good reproducibility.

For precision studies 5 replicated injections of Levothyroxine and Liothyronine formulation was performed. %RSD was determined for peak areas of Levothyroxine and Liothyronine.

The acceptance limits should be not more than 2% and the results were found to be within the acceptance limits.

The chromatogram of precision was showed in Figs: 29-33 results were reported in Table: 35

Ruggedness:**Table 7.29: Observation of Robustness Day 1**

S. No.	Sample Area 1	Sample Area 2
1	1665985	436598
2	1662598	436855
3	1668484	436598
4	1664598	436587
5	1663579	436741
6	1664587	432659
Mean	1664972	436006.3
Std. Dev.	2060.327	1643.285
% RSD	0.123745	0.376895

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Day 2:**Table 7.30: Observation of robustness Day 2**

S. No.	Sample Area 1	Sample Area 2
1	1648598	415985
2	1642587	415267
3	1649852	415986
4	1648754	415265
5	1645289	415874
6	1647581	415632
Mean	1647110	415668.2
Std. Dev.	2699.291	337.2106
% RSD	0.16388	0.081125

Acceptance Criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Linearity

Fig 7.47: Calibration Curve for Levothyroxine

Table 7.31: Linearity Observation of Levothyroxine

S. No	Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
1.	100	585985
2.	200	1182468
3.	300	1768785
4.	400	2326852
5.	500	2856874

Fig 7.48: Calibration Curve for Liothyronine

Table 7.32: Linearity Observation of Liothyronine

S. No.	Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
1	30	268764
2	40	356958
3	50	445631
4	60	535186
5	70	624698

The linearity range was found to be 100-500 and 30-70µg/ml for both Levothyroxine **and** Liothyronine respectively. Calibration curve was plotted and correlated Co-efficient for both the drugs found to be 0.999.

Robustness**Table : Flow rate Observation of Levothyroxine****System suitability Results for Levothyroxine**

Flow Rate (ml/min)		System suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
Less Flow rate	0.8	7365	1.62	1.868
Actual Flow rate	1	7586	1.69	1.688
More Flow rate	1.2	7254	1.61	1.544

Results for actual flow rate have been considered from assay standard.

Table: Flow rate Observation of Liothyronine**System suitability Results for Liothyronine**

Flow Rate (ml/min)		System suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
Less Flow rate	0.8	6284	1.51	3.621
Actual Flow rate	1	6235	1.58	3.282
More Flow rate	1.2	6168	1.56	2.998

On evaluation of the above results, it can be concluded that the variation in flow rate not affect the method significantly.

Table : System suitability results Levothyroxine

Organic phase		System suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
Less organic phase	50:50	7269	1.61	1.868
Actual organic phase	55:45	7586	1.69	1.688
More organic phase	60:40	7496	1.64	1.675

Table : System suitability result Liothyronine

Organic phase		System suitability Results		
		USP Plate Count	USP Tailing	Retention Time (min)
Less organic phase	50:50	6182	1.54	3.621
Actual organic phase	55:45	6235	1.58	3.282
More organic phase	60:40	6322	1.56	2.302

Acceptance Criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

In this study, a new RP-HPLC method was developed and validated for the simultaneous determination of Levothyroxine and Liothyronine in bulk and combined pharmaceutical dosage forms. The method utilized an Agilent Zorbax (C18) column with a mobile phase consisting of Methanol: Acetonitrile (25:75v/v), achieving separation within 8 minutes. Detection was performed at 265nm, ensuring adequate sensitivity across the concentration ranges of 100-500 µg/ml for Levothyroxine and 30-70 µg/ml for Liothyronine. Validation tests confirmed the method's reliability with respect to linearity, accuracy, precision, selectivity, and robustness, demonstrating its suitability for quality control laboratories. The method's robustness was further supported by %RSD values within acceptable limits, maintaining system suitability parameters.

In conclusion, the developed RP-HPLC method offers a straightforward yet effective approach for the simultaneous quantification of Levothyroxine and Liothyronine in both bulk materials and pharmaceutical formulations. The method's ability to achieve rapid separation, coupled with its high sensitivity and precise analytical performance, underscores its utility for routine analysis in pharmaceutical quality control settings. By providing accurate and reliable results within a short runtime, this method represents a significant advancement in the field of pharmaceutical analysis,

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